

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins Part XVII. Synthesis of Psoralene Derivatives

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Pechmann condensation of 2-methyl resorcinol with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate gave 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin and 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin respectively. These on allylation followed by Claisen rearrangement gave the corresponding 6-allyl derivative, which when treated with osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate gave the corresponding 6-(2'-oxoethyl) derivatives. These were cyclised to (IIIa) and (V) respectively. 6-Allyl derivatives were also cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to give the corresponding 2,3-dihydrofurocoumarin derivatives, which on dehydrogenation gave (IIIb) and (VII).

IN continuation of our work on the synthesis of psoralene derivatives^{2a,b,c,d}, we report here the synthesis of few more psoralene derivatives

Pechmann condensation of 2-methyl resorcinol with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate gave 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ia). This on allylation with allyl bromide gave 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ib), which when subjected to Claisen rearrangement afforded 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ic). (Ic), on treatment with Osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate gave 7-hydroxy-6-(2'-oxoethyl)-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Id) which showed following bands in the IR region: 3340 cm^{-1} (bonded—OH group), 1690 cm^{-1} (lactone $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ group) and 1670 cm^{-1} (—CHO group). (Id) on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid furnished 9-methyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIIa). 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ic) was also cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to give 2,9-dimethyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (II), which was dehydrogenated with palladium charcoal in diphenyl ether to give 2,9-dimethyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIIb).

2-Methyl resorcinol was also condensed with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate to give 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (IVa), which on allylation, followed by Claisen rearrangement gave 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (IVc). (IVc) when subjected to above series of reactions, it furnished 9-methyl-5,6-cyclohexeno-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (V) and 2,9-dimethyl-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzo (c) benzopyran (VII) respectively. The cyclohexeno ring was also dehydrogenated simultaneously to benzene ring.

Experimental

I.R. Spectra are determined with Perkin-Elmer grating spectrophotometer in nujol.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra are measured with Beckmann DU spectrophotometer in ethanol.

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ia): A mixture of 2-methyl resorcinol (5 g.) and ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (5 ml.) was slowly added to conc. sulphuric acid (15 ml.) kept in an ice bath with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was left for 6 hr. and then was added into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with water. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 259°. Yield 4 g. (Found: C, 72.35; H, 5.85. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 72.21; H, 5.56%).

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ib): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (3 g.), allyl bromide (3 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (300 ml.) in a water bath for 6 hrs. After the evaporation of acetone, the residue was treated with water. The product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 111°. Yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 75.13; H, 6.11. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.10; H, 6.25%).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Ic): 7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (8 ml.) for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid (25 ml.) containing pieces of ice. The contents were ether extracted and the ethereal layer was separated. It was shaken with sodium hydroxide solution (50 ml; 10%). The alkaline layer was separated and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered and it crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 170°. Yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 75.06; H, 6.12. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.01; H, 6.25%).

7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxoethyl)-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (Id): A solution of 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (500 mg.) in ethyl

acetate (100 ml.) was vigorously shaken with osmium tetroxide (50 mg.) and water (100 ml.). To the dark yellow solution was added potassium periodate (2 g, in 100 ml. water) during the period of 2 hrs. The ethyl acetate layer was separated, dried and evaporated. The residue was dissolved in chloroform and the clear solution was passed over a short column of alumina. Chloroform was evaporated and the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 190°. Yield 400 mg (Found : C, 69.81; H, 5.37. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.77; H, 5.43%).

9-Methyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIIa) : 7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxoethyl)-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (300 mg.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 ml) on a water bath for 20 mins. The reaction mixture was poured into ice water. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 223°. Yield 200 mg (Found : C, 74.84; H, 4.92. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 75.01; H, 5.00%).

λ_{max} (ethanol) 245 $m\mu$ (log 4.10), 295 (3.83); 322 (3.68).

2,9-Dimethyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (II) : 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclopentenocoumarin (1 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml.) in a water for 10 mins. The contents were poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 168°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 75.40; H, 6.29. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.01; H, 6.25%).

2,9-Dimethyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIIb) : A mixture of 2,9-dimethyl-5,6-cyclopenteno-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (0.5 g.), palladium charcoal (0.3 g.; 10%) and diphenyl ether (4 ml.) was refluxed for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and after cooling petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered was washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 208°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found; C, 76.05; H, 5.66. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.06; H, 5.51%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (IVa) : An ice cold mixture of 2-methyl resorcinol (5 g.) and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (7 ml.) was slowly added to sulphuric acid (15 ml.; 80%) kept in an ice bath with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was worked up as above and the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 268°. Yield 5 g. (Found : C, 73.43; H, 6.23. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.05; H, 6.08%).

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (IVb) : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (3 g.), allyl bromide (2.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (250 ml.). On working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 145°. Yield 2.5 g. (Found : C, 75.36; H, 6.39. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.53; H, 6.67%).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (IVc) : 7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-3,4-dicyclohexenocoumarin

(2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (8 ml.) for 6 hrs. Working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 163°. Yield 1.7 g. (Found : C, 75.25; H, 6.43; $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.53; H, 6.67%).

7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxoethyl)-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (IVd) : A solution of 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (500 mg) in ethyl acetate (100 ml) was vigorously shaken with osmium tetroxide (50 mg) and water (100 ml.). To the dark yellow solution potassium periodate (2 g in 100 ml water) was added dropwise over a period of 3 hrs Working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 183°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 70.42, H, 5.72. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.88%). IR spectrum : 3350, 1690, 1670 cm^{-1}

9-Methyl-5,6-cyclohexeno-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (V) : 7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxoethyl)-8-ethyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (250 mg) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (6 ml) in a water bath for 20 mins. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The chloroform extract of the dried residue, was passed over a short column of alumina. Evaporation of the solvent left the residue which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 192°. Yield 100 mg. (Found : C, 75.13; H, 5.42. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.55; H, 5.50%).

λ_{max} (ethanol) 242 $m\mu$ (log e 4.09), 292 (3.82), 322 (3.67).

2,9-Dimethyl-5,6-cyclohexeno-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (VI) : 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-cyclohexenocoumarin (1 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (8 ml.) in a water bath for 10 mins. Working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 169°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 75.48; H, 6.55. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.53; H, 6.67%).

2,9-Dimethyl-7-oxo-7H-furo(3,2-g) benzo (c) benzopyran (VII) : A mixture of 2,9-dimethyl-5,6-cyclohexeno-7-oxo-7H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (0.5 g) and palladised charcoal (0.3 g; 10%) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (4 ml.) for 7 hrs. Working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 227°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 77.57; H, 4.42. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.55%).

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